

Review of “A 3-D Constitutive Model for Finite Element Analyses of Agarose with a Range of Gel Concentrations”

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Article Reviewed: Xiaogang Wang, Ronald K. June, David M. Pierce. A 3-D Constitutive Model for Finite Element Analyses of Agarose with a Range of Gel Concentrations.

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Overview

In this manuscript, the authors develop and validate a constitutive model for agarose hydrogels implemented via finite element modeling. Strengths of the paper include the well described study design, the rigor of the approach, the comparison of multiple constitutive relationships, and the validation of the model with independent experimental data. Overall, the application of mechanics to study cell behavior in this model system may add new insights in mechanobiology and tissue engineering. It's a nice example of “functional” tissue engineering.

General and specific comments follow. We hope the authors find the feedback valuable, and we'd be happy to engage in a discussion if there are any questions.

General Comments

1. The authors mention that computational models, such as that developed in this study, can help determine whether stresses or strains primarily drive mechanotransduction, but it is not clear how this will be done. It would be helpful to include a description of how such a model can be implemented to determine whether stress or strain is the primary mechanism of mechanotransduction.
2. This manuscript does not discuss the constitutive model developed in this study in the context of previous models of agarose hydrogels in the introduction or discussion. There are several examples in the literature of computational modeling of agarose hydrogels with stiffness values similar to the current study. This study may have distinct advantages over this prior work, but this is not clear currently.
3. One issue to consider down the road is that the relationship between gel stiffness and cell response could be complex. The authors suggest that a lower gel stiffness may be more representative of an OA condition, but tissue engineering studies have shown that

lower gel density/stiffness can lead to improved mechanical properties of cell-seeded gels over time.

4. One issue with viscoelastic modeling is the assumption of instantaneous strain. Any thoughts on how this assumption may impact the modeling results?
5. How was the constitutive relationship developed in this study implemented within FEBio? A more detailed description would be useful. It's clear that the optimization scheme was used, but we weren't sure if new material models were implemented or if the approach used materials that already exist in FEBio.

Specific Comments

1. Page 3: How was the zero load condition established?
2. Page 3-4: Was the testing done with samples in PBS throughout?
3. Equation 1: Should the fluid phase also have a partial density associated with it?
4. Page 4: "We calculate the viscous contribution..." Should this be "elastic contribution?"
5. Fig. 1: Should the radius be 3.5mm?
6. Fig. 2: Statistical comparisons for data in Fig. 2(a) are described in the text. It would be helpful to represent these differences in the figure (or figure legend) as well. Additionally, it would be useful to show the results from both conditions with two VPs (one and two steps) in Fig. 2(b), since both are shown in part (a).
7. Page 9: It is difficult to determine how "good" these models are based on the objective function values (shown in Fig. 2). What is an acceptable or typical range for these values?
8. Table 2: The level of precision makes this table a bit hard to read.
9. Fig 3: While the bar graphs provide a general trend, providing the specific data points would be more powerful for showing the correlation.
10. Fig 3: The stdev bars are somewhat difficult to see and are a different color from other graphs.
11. Table 3/Figure 4: While the prestrain forces and peak reaction forces were similar to the predicted reaction forces, are the differences between the predicted and valley reaction forces significant/relevant? What is acceptable?